

Title: A protocol for karyotyping and genetic editing of induced pluripotent stem cells with homology-directed repair mediated CRISPR/Cas9

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Abstract

CRISPR/Cas9-mediated homology-directed repair (HDR) allows precise gene editing, but its efficiency remains low for certain cell types, such as human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs). In this study, we aimed to introduce the *CTNNA1*: c.2023C>T (p.Q675*) genetic alteration, which is associated with Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer, into hiPSCs using CRISPR/Cas9. We designed a single-guide RNA (sgRNA) targeting the alteration site and a single-stranded oligonucleotide donor DNA template for HDR-based repair. Herein, we report the successful introduction of the *CTNNA1*:c.2023C>T homozygous alteration in one hiPSC line, which resulted in severe phenotypic changes, including impaired colony formation and cell proliferation. Additionally, we established a straightforward protocol to assess hiPSCs karyotype integrity, ensuring the chromosomal stability required for the gene-editing process. This protocol involves routine G-banding analysis that is required for regular quality controls during handling of hiPSCs. This study demonstrates an efficient approach to precisely edit hiPSCs by CRISPR/Cas9 and highlights the essential role of *CTNNA1* expression in maintaining hiPSC viability. Our methodology provides a valuable framework for modeling disease-associated alterations in human-derived cellular models that can be reproduced for other genes and other types of cell lines.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in genome editing have revolutionized molecular biology in the past decade, with CRISPR/Cas9 emerging as a powerful tool for precise genetic manipulation. This editing technique, originally derived from bacterial adaptive immune system, allows for highly specific DNA targeting and the introduction of specific genetic alterations in the correct site. Being so versatile, CRISPR/Cas9 has become the method of choice for researchers studying gene function, disease modelling, and developing therapeutic strategies in various biological systems, including human cells [1, 2].

Genetic editing by CRISPR/Cas9 occurs due to two major DNA repair pathways, non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) and homology-directed repair (HDR). When Cas9 induces a double-strand break (DSB), NHEJ, the predominant pathway, quickly repairs the DSB, often introducing small insertions or deletions (indels) in the DSB region that can disrupt gene function [3]. This makes NHEJ very useful for gene knockout applications, where precision is not the main goal. In contrast, HDR, which occurs less frequently, uses a homologous DNA template to repair the DSB, allowing highly precise gene editing at the single-base level. Therefore, HDR is the best approach for precise introduction of specific genetic alterations such as point mutations or corrections [4]. Achieving high efficiency in HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 remains challenging [5] and over the past years, researchers have optimized CRISPR/Cas9 protocols to improve HDR efficacy [6]. Some of the strategies included optimizing the length and understanding the maximum conversion tract of HDR DNA donor templates [7-9]. Furthermore, strategies including a PAM silent alteration have shown to improve editing efficiency by preventing Cas9 re-cutting at the PAM site [10]. In particularly hard-to-edit cells cell types, such as human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs), these optimizations can be imperative to achieve a good efficiency in CRISPR/Cas9 precise gene editing.

HiPSCs research achieved a lot of success since their discovery in 2006 by Shinya Yamanaka [11]. These cells are derived by reprogramming adult somatic cells into a pluripotent state, which in turn, allows them to be differentiated virtually into any type of human cell [11]. Besides being an excellent research model due to their ability to give rise to different tissues, they have been considered a promising strategy for regenerative therapy, personalized human genetics, pharmacogenomics, and drug-screening studies [12, 13]. Particularly for rare diseases research, the use of hiPSCs is highly valuable to overcome many of their associated challenges, such as the establishment of cell lines that mimic the genetic background of affected individuals, which not only avoids some of

the ethical concerns associated with the use of embryonic stem cells but also decreases the use of animal models for research purposes [14]. Especially for cancer research, using hiPSCs allows to study the biological and molecular part of tumor initiation and development, and enables the modeling of genetic alterations that drive cancer progression [15]. Despite all these advantages, hiPSCs cell culture conditions are associated with genomic instability [16]. Therefore, it is important to guarantee the quality and integrity of these cells when in culture for long-term. G-banded karyotyping allows to detect numerical and structural chromosomal abnormalities and is a straightforward and low-cost technique [17]. If any abnormality is detected, hiPSCs should be discarded.

In this study, we aimed to establish a protocol to introduce a disease-relevant single nucleotide alteration in hiPSCs using HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9, while also optimizing hiPSC characterization methods, such as the G-band karyotyping protocol. For this, we selected the *CTNNA1* gene. *CTNNA1* encodes α E-catenin, a key player in the cadherin-catenin adhesion complex. Germline truncating alterations in *CTNNA1* have been associated with Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC), a very aggressive and rare hereditary cancer syndrome that predisposes for development of early onset diffuse gastric cancer and invasive lobular breast cancer [18, 19]. In our approach, we introduced one of the truncating *CTNNA1* variants associated with HDGC, the *CTNNA1*:c.2023C>T nonsense variant [20], that causes a premature termination codon in *CTNNA1* exon 15. We used a single-guide RNA (sgRNA) targeting the site of the alteration, alongside a single-stranded oligonucleotide (ssODN) donor DNA template designed for HDR-based DNA repair. We were further successful in implementing a G-band karyotyping protocol for hiPSCs culture maintenance, that could be easily performed in different labs.

We report an efficient HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 strategy for precise gene editing in hiPSCs and provide novel insights into the role of *CTNNA1* in non-differentiated cells. Our findings further demonstrate that introducing a nonsense alteration in *CTNNA1* in a homozygous state results in severe phenotypic changes, suggesting a role for α E-catenin in maintaining stable hiPSCs. This methodology can be applied broadly to investigate gene function in hiPSCs and model disease-relevant alterations in a controlled and reproducible manner, consistent with good handling of hiPSCs cultures.

2. Methodology

a) *Cell maintenance*

Gibco™ episomal hiPSC line (#A18945) was purchased from ThermoFisher (Waltham, MA, USA) and is a viral-integration-free hiPSC line, adapted to feeder-free, serum-free culture conditions. Cells were maintained in Matrigel-coated 6-well plates (Corning® Matrigel® hESC-qualified Matrix, #354277, Corning, NY, USA) and seeded in mTeSR™1 medium (#85850, StemCell Technologies, Vancouver, Canada) under 37°C and 5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator.

b) *Immunofluorescence for phenotypic assessment of pluripotent markers in hiPSCs*

Immunofluorescence analysis was performed to confirm the pluripotent state of Gibco™ episomal hiPSC line. For that we used the ES/iPSC Cell Characterization Kit from EMD Millipore (#SCR001; Burlington, MA, USA). Cells grew in glass coverslips for 3 days. Next, cells were washed in 1x PBS and fixed in 4% PFA (v/v) (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) for 20 minutes at room temperature (RT). All subsequent cell washes were performed using TBST (TBS with 0.1% Tween-20). Cells were incubated in 0,2% TritonX-100 (v/v) (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) in 1x PBS (5 minutes at RT) to permeabilize cell membrane. Afterwards, cells were incubated in the blocking solution (4% normal goat serum in 1x PBS for 30 minutes at RT), and subsequently, primary antibodies from the characterization kit were added: mouse anti-SSEA-1, mouse anti-SSEA-4, mouse anti-TRA-1-60 and mouse anti-TRA-1-81 (1:50; 1 hour incubation at RT). Secondary antibodies goat anti-mouse IgGs conjugated with Alexa Fluor 488 or Alexa Fluor 546 from Invitrogen were used (1:250; 1 hour incubation at RT). Finally, cells were incubated for 10 minutes at RT in 1µg/mL DAPI (#28718-90-3, Sigma-Aldrich, Poole, UK) in 1x PBS and coverslips were mounted in Vectashield anti-fade mounting media (Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA). Fluorescence was measured using the Leica SP5 confocal microscope and analysed using Leica Application Suite X (Leica, Wetzlar, Germany).

c) *Immunofluorescence for adherens' junction molecules*

Immunofluorescence analysis was performed to determine α E-catenin and E-cadherin protein expression in hiPSCs. Cells were plated and allowed to grow for 3 days in glass coverslips. Subsequently, media was discarded, cells were washed in 1x PBS and fixed in 4% PFA (v/v). Afterwards, NH₄Cl 50mM (v/v) in 1x PBS was added to decrease cell autofluorescence, cells were washed, and 0,2% TritonX-100 (v/v) in 1x PBS was added.

Next, 5% BSA (w/v) in 1X PBS was used as blocking solution and, subsequently, cells were incubated at 4°C overnight in a humidified chamber in α E-catenin and E-cadherin primary antibodies: mouse anti α -Catenin monoclonal antibody alpha-CAT-7A4 (1:200; ThermoFisher) or rabbit anti E-cadherin monoclonal antibody 24E10 (1:100; Cell Signalling). Further incubation with secondary antibodies was performed: Goat anti-Mouse or Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ Plus 647 (1:500, 2 hours incubation at room temperature). In the end, cells were incubated for 5 minutes in 1 μ g/mL DAPI and coverslips were mounted in Vectashield. Fluorescence was measured using the Leica SP5 confocal microscope and analysed using Leica Application Suite X (Leica, Wetzlar, Germany).

d) Karyotype analysis for hiPSC

Chromosome slides were prepared and GTL-banding was performed using Leishman stain (#L6254, Sigma) in accordance with established laboratory protocols. To analyze hiPSCs, a minimum of 20 metaphases were analyzed, following the guidelines of the International System for Human Cytogenomic Nomenclature (ISCN) [21]. Metaphases were karyotyped using the CytoVision/v3.932 software (Applied Imaging Cytovision). The detailed protocol for this technique is available in the Supplementary material.

e) Design of single guided RNA and a single-stranded oligonucleotide DNA donor template

Single guided RNA (gRNA) was designed with the WTSI Genome Editing (WGE) online tool (<https://www.sanger.ac.uk/tool/wge-crispr-design-tool/>). The gRNA was designed to target *CTNNA1* exon 15, specifically to perform the nonsense *CTNNA1:c.2023C>T* (p.Q675*) variant in a homozygous state. The gRNA was purchased from Alfacene (Carcavelos, Portugal) as forward and reverse sequences for further annealing to create a double stranded sgRNA: 5'- CACCGGATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCCC -3' (forward) and 5'- AAACGGGGAAGCTGAGCCATGATCC -3' (reverse). Underlined nucleotides correspond to the BbsI digestion motif, for proper ligation to the BbsI digested plasmid during the cloning protocol. A ssODN donor template was designed containing the desired alteration, as well as a silent mutation on the PAM site (*CTNNA1:c.2034G>A*; p.Q678=), and was purchased from IDT (Coralville, IA, USA): 5'- GCTTCTGATCACAGGCGATCATGGCTIAGCTTCCCCAAGAGCAAAAAGCGAAGATT GCGGAACAGGTGGCCAGCTTCCAGGAAGAAAAGAGCAAGCTGGATGCTGAAGTG TCCAAATGGGACGACAG -3'. This further contained an Alt-R HDR modification variation from IDT to improve stability upon delivery to cells.

The sgRNA was cloned into the pSpCas9(BB)-2A-GFP (PX458) vector from Addgene (#48138; Watertown, MA, USA), which contains the Cas9 gene from *S. pyogenes*, a GFP selection marker cassette and the PX458 vector backbone. 1µg of pSpCas9(BB)-2A-GFP (PX458) vector was digested using 10 units of the BbsI restriction enzyme from New England Biolabs (#R0539S; Ipswich, MA, USA). sgRNA forward and reverse sequences were annealed to form a double chain sequence and ligated to the vector using 200 units of T4 DNA ligase from New England Biolabs (#M0202S). A 1:1 vector:sgRNA ligation ratio was used and ligation was performed at 16°C overnight. 2µL of ligation reaction were further transformed in 50µL of competent *E. coli* cells (Stbl3). Three colonies were picked for subsequent sanger sequencing to confirm the insertion of the sgRNA. One positive colony was then expanded and the QIAGEN Maxiprep kit (#12362, Hilden, Germany) was used to isolate highly pure plasmids, following the manufacturer's instructions.

f) Cas9 plasmid and ssODN donor template electroporation

The plasmid containing the Cas9 and the sgRNA, as well as the ssODN donor template were delivered to hiPSCs through electroporation. Briefly, fresh mTeSR™1 medium containing 10mM ROCK inhibitor was added to hiPSCs for one hour. Afterwards, cells were detached and resuspended to a single cell state. Cells were counted and 6×10^6 cells were resuspended in nucleofector reagent from the P3 Primary Cell 4D-Nucleofector™ X Kit from Lonza (Basilea, Switzerland). Cells were then placed carefully in a nucleocuvette vessel to avoid the presence of bubbles and were subsequently electroporated in the Lonza 4D-nucleofector system. After electroporation, the nucleocuvette vessels containing the cells were incubated at 37°C for 15 minutes. Finally, electroporated cells were plated in Matrigel-coated plates containing fresh mTeSR™1 medium with 10mM ROCK inhibitor. After 24 hours, 10mM ROCK inhibitor was retrieved from cells and these were allowed to grow before cell sorting. For the optimization step of the electroporation protocol, three programs already used in human iPSCs were tested (CM-100, CM-130, CB150) [22-24]. Only the most successful electroporation program was used in the CRISPR/Cas9 experiment, namely the CM-130 program.

g) FACS cell sorting

After electroporation, cells were allowed to recover and grow for 72 hours. Before starting the cell sorting protocol, cells were incubated in 10mM ROCK inhibitor for one hour. Afterwards, media was removed, cells were detached and resuspended in mTeSR™1 with 10mM ROCK inhibitor. Next, cells were centrifuge at 200g for 10 minutes and

resuspended in 400µL of mTeSR™1 containing 10mM ROCK inhibitor. Cell suspension was filtered using a 40µm pore filter and placed in a sterile cytometer tube. Cells were then sorted for GFP positive expression using the FACS Aria II cell sorter from BD Biosciences (Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA). Finally, GFP+ cells were plated in a 10cm Matrigel-coated petri dish containing fresh mTeSR™1 medium with 10mM ROCK inhibitor. After 24 hours, cells were retrieved from the 10mM ROCK inhibitor and allowed to grow. GFP positive expression was analyzed using the ZOE™ Fluorescent Cell Imager from Bio-Rad (Hercules, CA, USA).

h) Genotyping of CRISPR/Cas9 hiPSC clones

Clones derived from cell sorting were isolated and allowed to grow separately in 12-well plates. Afterwards, gDNA was extracted using the NZY Tissue gDNA Isolation kit from NZYTech (Lisbon, Portugal), according to the manufacturer's protocol. DNA concentration and quality was measured with NanoDrop® One UV-Vis. DNA quality was assessed by Abs260/Abs280 ratio above 1.80. The extracted genomic DNA was then used to perform a set of genotyping PCRs. Multiplex PCR kit from Qiagen was used to amplify *CTNNA1* exon 15 by using primers in the adjacent intronic areas. A short ~400 bp and a long ~2 Kb sequence spanning from intron 14 to intron 15 were analyzed. The primers used for the short analysis were the following: 5' ACCTATGCCACAGATTGCCT 3' (forward); 5' GCCCCTCACAGTTGGAGTAG 3' (reverse). The primers used for the long analysis were the following: 5' AGAAAGCCAGTCAGAGCCAT 3' (forward); 5' GAGGCTCCCAGATTAGGACC 3' (reverse). PCR products were analyzed by electrophoresis through a 1.5% agarose gel with GreenSafe premium dye from NZYTech and a Gel Doc™ XR+ Gel Documentation System from Bio-Rad was used to reveal the electrophoresis. In clones with more than one band, bands were cut and DNA was purified using the illustra™ triplePrep kit from GE HealthCare (Chicago, IL, USA). In clones presenting only one band, PCR product was purified with ExoSAP-IT PCR Product Cleanup Reagent from Applied Biosystems (Waltham, MA, USA). All clones were sanger sequenced to confirm the presence or absence of genetic editing using the BigDye™ Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit from Applied Biosystems and the same genotyping primers, and were analyzed using the Applied Biosystems 3130xl Genetic Analyzer. Samples presenting more than one sequence in the Sanger sequencing file were deconvoluted using the Mutation Surveyor v5.2.0 tool ([State College, PA, USA](#)) and manually confirmed.

3. Results

To test the HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 protocol, we mimicked the *CTNNA1*:c.2023C>T (p.Q675*) nonsense variant, causing *CTNNA1* truncation and *CTNNA1* loss-of-function [19, 20]. The entire study workflow is described in Fig.1.

Figure 1 - Study design. We introduced the *CTNNA1*:c.2023C>T (p.Q675*) nonsense variant into hiPSCs. For that, we designed a sgRNA to drive Cas9 into the target location of the c.2023C>T alteration, and a ssODN HDR donor template to be used by cells as a DNA repair template, after Cas9 DSB. We cloned the sgRNA into a pSpCas9(BB)-2A-GFP(PX458), which contains the Cas9 gene and a GFP selection marker. We delivered both the plasmid and the ssODN template to hiPSCs by electroporation and submitted them to FACS cell sorting to select GFP+ cells. Sorted cells were allowed to grow and the new colonies were isolated and genotyped to assess the success of HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 genetic editing.

a) *Characterization of genomic stability and expression of pluripotency markers is essential prior to genomic editing in hiPSCs*

Confirming the pluripotency potential of the hiPSC line to be used is the first step before starting genetic editing with the HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 protocol. For this, it is essential to select markers, not only to characterize hiPSCs, but also to monitor pluripotency in cultures over time. We selected TRA-1-60, TRA-1-81 and SSEA-4 as pluripotency markers, and SSEA-1 as a negative control. TRA-1-60 and TRA-1-81 are

high-molecular-weight cell surface glycoproteins expressed by human ESCs and hiPSCs. SSEA-4 and SSEA-1 are cell surface antigens, while SSEA-4 is commonly expressed in hiPSCs, SSEA-1 expression is negative in these cells [25].

We used the Gibco Episomal hiPSC Line (A18945, ThermoFisher), derived from the cord blood of a newborn female, confirmed cultures were mycoplasma-free (data not shown), and used immunocytochemistry to characterize the expression of TRA-1-60, TRA-1-81, and SSEA-4 and SSEA-1. This analysis confirmed that the Gibco Episomal hiPSC Line is negative for SSEA-1, while SSEA-4, TRA-1-60 and TRA-1-81 are expressed at the membrane (Fig.2A). The expression profile of these markers supports the pluripotency of the selected cell line to be used.

Since we wanted to edit the *CTNNA1* gene to mimic a genetic alteration predicted to cause *CTNNA1* loss of expression, it was important to confirm that the cadherin-catenin adhesion complex was intact, validating the proper expression of α E-catenin, as well as E-cadherin adhesion molecule. We confirmed, by immunohistochemistry, that both α E-catenin and E-cadherin proteins display a membranous expression and are concomitantly expressed in hiPSCs (Fig.2B).

To assess chromosomal stability and exclude potential chromosomal abnormalities that can occur during hiPSC line culture, we performed the karyotype using GTL-banding. The cytogenetic analysis consisted in the observation of at least 20 metaphases, counting and analyzing the structure of all chromosomes by an experienced cytogeneticist. For all the cells analyzed, a normal female chromosomal complement (46,XX) was observed (Fig.2C).

b) Development of an HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 strategy for targeting the CTNNA1: c.2023C>T variant

- I. Proximity to the target mutation site is a priority for optimized sgRNA and ssODN donor template design for efficient editing

To design the sgRNA, we used WTSI Genome Editing (WGE) online tool. Here, we analysed the presence of Cas9 PAM in the vicinity of the position to be modified. We identified an "AGG" PAM motif 9bp downstream of the c.2023 nucleotide. Cas9 is expected to cause a DSB 3-4bp upstream this motif. Thus, the c.2023 nucleotide is expected to be located 5-6bp upstream the DBS site. Previous studies have demonstrated that the efficacy of HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 significantly drops with the increasing distance to the mutation site, with efficacy dropping to half if this distance is longer than 10bp [26]. We designed a 21bp long sgRNA that target the sequence right

upstream of the PAM motif mentioned above (Fig.3A). This sgRNA was selected especially due to its proximity to the mutation target site. The 21bp length for the sgRNA was selected to ensure a favourable on-target specificity, while not increasing the off-target effects.

Figure 2 - Molecular characterization of wild-type hiPSCs. Immunocytochemistry analysis of the expression of: (A) SSEA-1 (red), SSEA-4 (red), TRA-1-60 (green) and TRA-1-81 (green); (B) α E-catenin (red) and E-cadherin (green). The coloring of DAPI is represented in blue. (C) Karyotype analysis of wild-type hiPSCs.

We next designed a ssODN HDR donor template to be used as a template to correct the DSB caused by Cas9. For this, we used the Alt-R HDR Design Tool (IDT) and further followed the Addgene guidelines to optimize donor DNA templates to improve HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 editing [27]. With this tool, we designed a 127bp long ssODN, containing asymmetric homology arms with 36bp on the PAM-distal arm and 91bp on the PAM-proximal arm of the DSB (Fig.3B). This ssODN contained the desired alteration (c.2023C>T), as well as a silent alteration in the 2nd nucleotide of the PAM sequence (AGG to AAG). This alteration, *CTNNA1*: c.2034G>A, is synonymous and does not change α E-catenin amino acid sequence (p.Q678=) (Fig.3). Cas9 can be active in cells for several hours, leading to Cas9 recutting after introducing the desired alteration, because it still recognizes the PAM sequence [28]. The introduction of the PAM silent mutation was intentional, as it leads to non-recognition of the PAM sequence by Cas9, once the ssODN template is integrated, preventing recutting of edited cells.

Figure 3 - Design and optimization of sgRNA and ssODN donor template for *CTNNA1* editing. (A) The WTSI Genome Editing (WGE) online tool was used to design the sgRNA. A BbsI motif was added to the sgRNA sequence in order to properly ligate to PX458 vector after BbsI digestion. (B) The ssODN HDR template was designed using the Alt-R HDR Design Tool from IDT. We also followed the guidelines provided by Addgene blog to optimize donor DNA template to improve HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 genetic editing.

II. Validation of off-target effects in HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9

One key point of CRISPR/Cas9-mediated genetic editing is the high specificity for the target site. For this, the sgRNA sequence must present a low off-target effect. We used the WTSI Genome Editing (WGE) online tool to further identified candidate off-target regions with sequence similarity to the on-target Cas9 site. We identified 241 off-target sites associated with the sgRNA sequence. Of these, 89.1% (215) presented at-least 4 mismatches to the sgRNA sequence, while 25/241 (10.4%) presented 3 mismatches, significantly impairing the recognition of these regions by the sgRNA [29-31]. One off-target presented only 1 mismatch (0.4%) to the sgRNA sequence in the most 3' nucleotide of the sequence, right before the PAM site. This off-target site was located in chromosome 5:115390356-115390378, a non-coding intergenic region identified as *CTNNA1P1* [32]. A detailed description of all off-target sites is provided in Supplementary Table 1.

III. Optimization of electroporation and flow cytometry allows selection of CRISPR-edited hiPSCs using HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9

To introduce the Cas9+sgRNA plasmid and the ssODN HDR donor template, we electroporated hiPSCs. For that, we used the P3 Primary Cell 4D-Nucleofector™ X Kit and the 4D-nucleofector system from Lonza. To assess the successful introduction of plasmid DNA using this method, we carried out an optimization step using a GFP+ commercial plasmid (Fig.4A). Here, we electroporated hiPSCs using three different electroporation programs (CM-100, CM-130 and CB-150) to introduce the pmaxGFP® plasmid, a control commercial vector containing the GFP fluorescent marker. CM-130 electroporation program presented the higher percentage of GFP+ cells (13.5%) when comparing to CM-100 (1.17%) or CB-150 (6.42%) (Fig.4A). Qualitative analysis of GFP expression further confirms that CM-130 electroporation program displayed more cells expressing GFP fluorescent marker.

Afterwards, we electroporated the Cas9 plasmid and ssODN donor template under the CM-130 program, and further selected GFP+ cells with FACS sorting. GFP+ cells selection was performed 72 hours after electroporation, which allowed cell recovery. Cells were detached to achieve a single cell state and, right after, hiPSCs were sorted for GFP. Our results demonstrate that 2.5% of all cells expressed GFP (Fig.4B). The 522 GFP+ cells were all plated in one 10 cm Petri dish coated in Matrigel®. For the subsequent 24 hours, cells were maintained in mTeSR1 with 10mM ROCK inhibitor to help single-cells recovering. GFP expression qualitative analysis confirmed expression of GFP in FACS sorted cells.

Figure 4 - Selection of CRISPR/Cas9 edited hiPSCs. (A) Optimization of the electroporation program for hiPSCs. Graphs represent FACS cell sorting experiments and images represent the respective GFP expression analysis. (B) Selection of GFP+ cells after CRISPR/Cas9 editing. The 1st graph selected the population of cells expected to be alive (live cells); the 2nd graph selected the population of cells expected to be in a singlet state (single cells); the 3rd graph selected the GFP+ cells that were further sorted to a 10cm petri dish with fresh Matrigel® and medium and allowed to grow for the subsequent days. The table follows the same scheme, presenting the quantification of cells and the respective percentage. Image represent the respective GFP expression analysis. Scalebars represent 100µm.

IV. Genotypic analysis reveals variable editing efficiency and outcomes in hiPSC clones following HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 editing

After FACS sorting, 522 cells were plated in one 10cm Petri dish, from which 24 clones grew and were selected for colony picking and expansion. For the colony-picking technique, it is crucial that colonies are large and isolated with well-established borders.

Each picked colony was transferred to a new freshly Matrigel® coated well of a 12-well plate using a 10µL pipette tip, cultured in cell medium with 10mM ROCK inhibitor. Of the 24 transferred clones, 29% (7/24; clones #7, 9, 14, 15, 19, 21 and 22) did not survive the post-transfer period. The remaining 17 clones were expanded (Fig.5A), and gDNA was extracted for genotyping analysis (Fig.1). Our results demonstrate that 47% (8/17) of all clones presented only mutated cells (Fig.5A-B). One clone (#1) presented both mutated and WT sequences. Of all clones, the DNA repair mechanism used after Cas9 cutting was HDR in 1/17 (6%) and NHEJ in 8/17 (47%) (Fig.5A). Clone #8, the only where HDR-mediated DNA repair was achieved, presented in an homozygous state the *CTNNA1*:c.2023C>T (p.Q675*) target alteration, as well as the PAM silent *CTNNA1*:c.2034G>A (p.Q678=) that was added to the ssODN HDR donor template to prevent Cas9 recutting. Three clones (#16, 20 and 23) also presented the PAM silent alteration, but were WT for the c.2023C>T target alteration. This indicates that the HDR template was integrated, however, the c.2023C>T desired alteration did not occur (Fig.5A). Regarding the NHEJ-mediated DNA repaired clones, a pleiotropy of different indels could be observed (Fig.5A-B). Clone #1 presented a 13bp deletion, as well as two different insertions of ~500bp and ~400bp, respectively. Clones #2, 12, 13 and 24 all presented two different sequences containing small deletions, with one being in-frame and one frameshift. Clones #5 and 6 presented two different sequences, one containing a 1bp deletion causing a frameshift alteration, and one 238bp-long deletion that leads to the in-frame deletion of 24bp in exon 15. Moreover, clone #18 presents one 226bp out-of-frame large insertion and one 1098bp large deletion. In this case, the large deletion leads to a premature stop codon only in the end of exon 18, *CTNNA1* last exon, that is predicted to escape nonsense mediated mRNA decay, thus leading to a shorter but functional protein [33, 34]. Of all successfully edited clones, only clone #8 presented a drastic change in cell phenotype, while all other clones revealed no phenotypic alterations (Fig.5C). These results further demonstrated that the PAM silent homozygous alteration, alone, does not cause any phenotype changes. Furthermore, 29% (5/17) of all clones (#3, 4, 10, 11 and 17) did not presented any genetic edition, either in the target site nor in the PAM motif (Fig.5A-B).

A 522 GFP+ cells were FACS sorted to a 10cm Matrigel® coated plate → 24 colonies were individually transferred to 12-well plates → 17/24 colonies survived and gDNA was genotyped

Clone no.*	Sequences found (N)	Sequence 1	Sequence 2	Other sequences	Predicted αE-cat expression	Phenotype	PAM mutated?
1	4	WT	13bp deletion (Frameshift alteration; disrupts the ORF in <i>CTNNA1</i> exon 15)	~500bp and ~400 insertions (breakpoints not determined) [‡]	Normal	Normal	NO
2	2	3bp deletion (In-frame deletion of 3bp in exon 15; does not disrupts the ORF)	13bp deletion (Frameshift alteration; disrupts the ORF in <i>CTNNA1</i> exon 15)	-	Normal (1 amino acid shorter protein)	Normal	NO
3	1	WT	-	-	Normal	Normal	NO
4	1	WT	-	-	Normal	Normal	NO
5	2	1bp del (Frameshift alteration; disrupts the ORF in <i>CTNNA1</i> exon 15)	238bp deletion (In-frame deletion of 24bp in exon 15; does not disrupts the ORF)	-	Normal (8 amino acid shorter protein)	Normal	NO
6	2	1bp del (Frameshift alteration; disrupts the ORF in <i>CTNNA1</i> exon 15)	238bp deletion (In-frame deletion of 24bp in exon 15; does not disrupts the ORF)	-	Normal (8 amino acid shorter protein)	Normal	NO
8	1	<i>CTNNA1</i> :c.20323C>T nonsense alteration	-	-	Loss-of-expression	Severe cell adhesion and proliferation loss	YES
10	1	WT	-	-	Normal	Normal	NO
11	1	WT	-	-	Normal	Normal	NO
12	2	9bp deletion (In-frame deletion of 9bp in exon 15; does not disrupts the ORF)	2bp deletion (Frameshift alteration; disrupts the ORF in <i>CTNNA1</i> exon 15)	-	Normal (3 amino acid shorter protein)	Normal	NO
13	2	9bp deletion (In-frame deletion of 9bp in exon 15; does not disrupts the ORF)	8bp deletion (Frameshift alteration; disrupts the ORF in <i>CTNNA1</i> exon 15)	-	Normal (3 amino acid shorter protein)	Normal	NO
16	1	WT	-	-	Normal	Normal	YES
17	1	WT	-	-	Normal	Normal	NO
18	2	6bp deletion + 226bp insertion (Frameshift out-of-frame alteration; disrupts the ORF)	1098bp deletion (out-of-frame large deletion; only disrupts the ORF deep into <i>CTNNA1</i> last exon)	-	Normal (31 amino acid shorter protein)	Normal	NO
20	1	WT	-	-	Normal	Normal	YES
23	1	WT	-	-	Normal	Normal	YES
24	2	9bp deletion (In-frame deletion of 9bp in exon 15; does not disrupts the ORF)	17bp deletion (Frameshift alteration; disrupts the ORF in <i>CTNNA1</i> exon 15)	-	Normal (3 amino acid shorter protein)	Normal	NO

*Only clones surviving colony transfer are depicted; [‡]The two large insertions from clone #1 are highlighted in (B).

B Clone: 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 10 11 12 13 16 17 18 20 23 24 CTR-

C Parental cell line (No editing, Wild-type PAM) Colony 20 (No editing, PAM mutated) Colony 8 (Correct editing, PAM mutated)

Figure 5 - Characterization of CRISPR/Cas9 genetic edited hiPSCs. (A) Detailed description of the clones that were successfully genotyped for the presence/absence of HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 genetic alterations; (B) Electrophoresis displaying the genotyping of the CTNNA1 sequence in the vicinity of the DSB Cas9 site of the clones; (C) Sanger sequencing and macroscopic phenotype of WT hiPSCs, hiPSCs presenting only the homozygous silent PAM alteration (c.2034G>A), and hiPSCs presenting both the homozygous target alteration (c.2023C>T) and the homozygous silent PAM alteration (c.2034G>A).

Genotyping analysis of the *CTNNA1P1* off-target site revealed that off-target Cas9 cleavage occurred in 63% (10/16; clone #13 was not successfully sequenced) of all clones (Supplementary Fig.1). Herein, eight clones (#1, 2, 8, 12, 16, 18, 20, 23) presented two sequences of the *CTNNA1P1* off-target site, one WT and one containing small indels. Furthermore, clones #5 and 6 contained only a 150bp deletion around the off-target site, and no WT sequence was found.

c) hiPSCs require an intact CTNNA1 locus for colonies viability and proliferation

We performed a microscopic analysis on the edited clones and our results demonstrated that only the nonsense *CTNNA1* variant c.2023C>T (p.Q675*) was deleterious to hiPSCs. This homozygous genetic alteration resulted in a severe loss of adhesion phenotype, and in a critical impact in cell viability, incompatible with colony survival. Ultimately, this clone was not viable due to impaired cell proliferation, resulting in the total loss of this isogenic hiPSC line (Fig.5B-C). Furthermore, all other edited clones presented a phenotype identical to the WT hiPSC line. This was expected since all edited clones presented at least a WT or an in-frame mutated sequence that is predicted to not disrupt the open reading frame of *CTNNA1*/αE-catenin.

4. Discussion

In the current study, we report the use of HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 to cause a specific nucleotide alteration (*CTNNA1:c.2023C>T*) in hiPSCs in less than two months, as well as a fully optimized unexpensive karyotyping protocol for proper iPSCs culture maintenance. The correct characterization of hiPSC cultures regarding genomic instability and pluripotency is mandatory before their experimental applications. In vitro culture of hiPSCs and their associated genetic reprogramming can cause chromosomal abnormalities. Therefore, the lack of genomic instability is an important safety concern that can hamper studies with hiPSCs and their applications.

CRISPR/Cas9-induced DSBs can be primarily repaired by either HDR or NHEJ [3, 35]. To obtain a precise genetic editing, HDR is the preferred pathway [4, 35], as the mutation we induced in the current study. The introduction of precise single base editions by HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 into human in vitro models, such as hiPSCs, holds significant importance to study the functional impact of specific genetic alterations. This is imperative in the study of hereditary syndromes, where specific disease-relevant single nucleotide alterations are found in affected individuals [36]. Previous studies have demonstrated that delivering a HDR donor DNA template can significantly improve the precision of repair, when comparing to traditional NHEJ [35]. Nevertheless, HDR presents a lower efficiency in most cells when compared to NHEJ, because it is restricted to the S and G2 phases of the cell cycle, when a homologous template is available [5]. Herein, we confirmed that HDR efficiency rate (6%) was considerably lower than NHEJ efficiency rate (47%). Thus, it is important to apply other strategies besides the donor DNA template that will allow cells to correct DNA through HDR to the detriment of NHEJ. Several studies have shown that, instead of inducing DSBs, which leads to correction by both HDR and NHEJ, inducing single-strand breaks favour HDR over NHEJ. This can be achieved by using nickase variants of Cas9 [37]. Furthermore, the low success rate of integrating the Cas9 vector into cells is a limitation in the present study. Although we present a very fast cell selection method with GFP+ cells being selected only 72h after plasmid electroporation, our results still demonstrate that only in 2.5% of cells, the delivery of the Cas9 vector was successful. hiPSCs are known to be a challenging type of cells to perform CRISPR/Cas9. Furthermore, plasmid delivery techniques present an inherent toxicity to cells [15]. It is likely that many of the hiPSCs do not survive the successful delivery of the plasmid, resulting in death. Thus, improving the method to deliver Cas9 and sgRNA to the cells is an urgent need. It has been demonstrated that using Cas9-sgRNA ribonucleoprotein complexes (RNPs) instead of Cas9 plasmids holds

significant improvements in genetic editing efficacy. A study performed by Xu and colleagues in 2021 demonstrated that using RNPs to introduce a 34bp sequence in a hiPSC line resulted in a 40% efficiency [38]. Since the delivery occurs in a protein complex, it is not dependent on Cas9 translation, leading to a faster Cas9 activity [39]. Furthermore, RNPs have been shown to improve editing efficiency in hard-to-transfect cells [40], which is the case of hiPSC lines.

We successfully developed a *CTNNA1*:c.2023C>T (p.Q675*) homozygous isogenic hiPSC line using our CRISPR/Cas9 strategy, which further enabled us to understand the functional impact of this genetic alteration in non-differentiated cells. However, in certain disease contexts, obtaining a heterozygous cell line could be important. To achieve this, altering the cell sorting protocol from bulk to single cell sorting would be required. Our results demonstrate that inducing the *CTNNA1*:c.2023C>T (p.Q675*) homozygous nonsense alteration in an hiPSC line leads to a severe phenotype. Indeed, cells from clone #8, the homozygous edited cells containing the *CTNNA1*:c.2023C>T nonsense alteration, present an impacted capacity to form colonies and a severely impacted capacity to divide and proliferate. Nevertheless, other studies developed in our laboratory have demonstrated that homozygous editing of *CTNNA1* in terminally differentiated cells does not cause such a severe phenotype, pinpointing towards the important role of *CTNNA1*/αE-catenin proper expression in non-differentiated cells [41]. Studies have demonstrated that αE-catenin is a known critical molecule for cellular adhesion and signalling pathways that are essential for early development. In a mouse model, conditional knockout of murine αE-catenin homologue protein in epidermal cells led to extreme defects in skin, limbs and hair follicles of mice, displaying defects in adherens' junction formation, intercellular adhesion, and epithelial polarity [20]. Furthermore, previous research developed by us [41] and others [42] in *Drosophila* have shown that knockout of *Drosophila* α-catenin homologue protein often induces lethality. Supporting these observations, Sarpal and colleagues reported that *Drosophila* α-catenin null embryos cannot properly develop, leading to embryonic death [42]. This is consistent with an important role for αE-catenin in embryonic development, and pinpoints towards its importance to maintain cultures of stable hiPSC lines. One limitation of this study is the direct consequence of the essential role of *CTNNA1* gene in mammalian cells. Although clone #8 presents the desired alteration in this study, with the severe impaired viability observed in this clone, no further analysis regarding RNA and protein were possible to perform.

Ultimately, with this study, we report an efficient method to obtain a precise genetic editing using HDR-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 in hiPSCs. The karyotyping protocol herein described is also an easy-to-implement, affordable protocol specifically tailored for the characterization of hiPSCs. This protocol offers researchers a streamlined and accessible alternative to outsourcing karyotyping to external companies, thus reducing dependency on third-party services and associated costs. By enabling in-lab assessment, this method empowers researchers to directly verify the genomic stability of their hiPSC lines, ensuring that the cells meet essential quality control standards for downstream applications. Due to its simplicity, our strategy can be further applied to different genes and different cell lines, including hard to edit cell lines.

5. References

1. Doudna JA, Charpentier E. Genome editing. The new frontier of genome engineering with CRISPR-Cas9. *Science* (New York, NY). 2014;346(6213):1258096. doi: 10.1126/science.1258096.
2. Hsu PD, Lander ES, Zhang F. Development and applications of CRISPR-Cas9 for genome engineering. *Cell*. 2014;157(6):1262-78. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2014.05.010.
3. Chang HHY, Pannunzio NR, Adachi N, Lieber MR. Non-homologous DNA end joining and alternative pathways to double-strand break repair. *Nature reviews Molecular cell biology*. 2017;18(8):495-506. doi: 10.1038/nrm.2017.48.
4. Ceccaldi R, Rondinelli B, D'Andrea AD. Repair Pathway Choices and Consequences at the Double-Strand Break. *Trends in cell biology*. 2016;26(1):52-64. doi: 10.1016/j.tcb.2015.07.009.
5. Jasin M, Haber JE. The democratization of gene editing: Insights from site-specific cleavage and double-strand break repair. *DNA repair*. 2016;44:6-16. doi: 10.1016/j.dnarep.2016.05.001.
6. Liu M, Rehman S, Tang X, Gu K, Fan Q, Chen D, et al. Methodologies for Improving HDR Efficiency. *Front Genet*. 2018;9:691. doi: 10.3389/fgene.2018.00691.
7. Elliott B, Richardson C, Winderbaum J, Nickoloff JA, Jasin M. Gene conversion tracts from double-strand break repair in mammalian cells. *Mol Cell Biol*. 1998;18(1):93-101. doi: 10.1128/mcb.18.1.93.
8. Kan Y, Ruis B, Takasugi T, Hendrickson EA. Mechanisms of precise genome editing using oligonucleotide donors. *Genome Res*. 2017;27(7):1099-111. doi: 10.1101/gr.214775.116.
9. Song F, Stieger K. Optimizing the DNA Donor Template for Homology-Directed Repair of Double-Strand Breaks. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids*. 2017;7:53-60. doi: 10.1016/j.omtn.2017.02.006.
10. McBeath E, Parker-Thornburg J, Fujii Y, Aryal N, Smith C, Hofmann MC, et al. Rapid Evaluation of CRISPR Guides and Donors for Engineering Mice. *Genes (Basel)*. 2020;11(6). doi: 10.3390/genes11060628.
11. Takahashi K, Yamanaka S. Induction of pluripotent stem cells from mouse embryonic and adult fibroblast cultures by defined factors. *Cell*. 2006;126(4):663-76. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2006.07.024.
12. Chehelgerdi M, Behdarvand Dehkordi F, Chehelgerdi M, Kabiri H, Salehian-Dehkordi H, Abdolvand M, et al. Exploring the promising potential of induced pluripotent stem cells in cancer research and therapy. *Molecular cancer*. 2023;22(1):189. doi: 10.1186/s12943-023-01873-0.
13. Shi Y, Inoue H, Wu JC, Yamanaka S. Induced pluripotent stem cell technology: a decade of progress. *Nature reviews Drug discovery*. 2017;16(2):115-30. doi: 10.1038/nrd.2016.245.
14. Niemitz E. Isogenic iPSC-derived models of disease. *Nature Genetics*. 2014;46(1):7-. doi: 10.1038/ng.2864.
15. Rowe RG, Daley GQ. Induced pluripotent stem cells in disease modelling and drug discovery. *Nature reviews Genetics*. 2019;20(7):377-88. doi: 10.1038/s41576-019-0100-z.
16. Yoshihara M, Oguchi A, Murakawa Y. Genomic Instability of iPSCs and Challenges in Their Clinical Applications. *Advances in experimental medicine and biology*. 2019;1201:23-47. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-31206-0_2.

17. Vaz IM, Borgonovo T, Kasai-Brunswick TH, Santos DSD, Mesquita FCP, Vasques JF, et al. Chromosomal aberrations after induced pluripotent stem cells reprogramming. *Genetics and molecular biology*. 2021;44(3):e20200147. doi: 10.1590/1678-4685-gmb-2020-0147.
18. Blair VR, McLeod M, Carneiro F, Coit DG, D'Addario JL, van Dieren JM, et al. Hereditary diffuse gastric cancer: updated clinical practice guidelines. *The Lancet Oncology*. 2020;21(8):e386-e97. doi: 10.1016/s1470-2045(20)30219-9.
19. Lobo S, Benusiglio PR, Coulet F, Boussemart L, Golmard L, Spier I, et al. Cancer predisposition and germline CTNNA1 variants. *European journal of medical genetics*. 2021;64(10):104316. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmg.2021.104316.
20. Benusiglio PR, Colas C, Guillerm E, Canard A, Delhomelle H, Warcoin M, et al. Clinical implications of CTNNA1 germline mutations in asymptomatic carriers. *Gastric cancer : official journal of the International Gastric Cancer Association and the Japanese Gastric Cancer Association*. 2019;22(4):899-903. doi: 10.1007/s10120-018-00907-7.
21. ISCN 2020: An International System for Human Cytogenomic Nomenclature (2020) Reprint of 'Cytogenetic and Genome Research 2020, Vol. 160, No. 7-8'. McGowan-Jordan J, Hastings RJ, Moore S, editors: S.Karger AG; 2020 29 Oct 2020. doi: 10.1159/isbn.978-3-318-06867-2.
22. Duboscq-Bidot L, Hoareau B, Ader F, Fontaine V, Villard E. Generation of CRISPR-Cas9 edited human induced pluripotent stem cell line carrying BAG3 V468M mutation in its BAG domain. *Stem Cell Res*. 2024;74:103294. doi: 10.1016/j.scr.2023.103294.
23. Luo Y, Rao M, Zou J. Generation of GFP Reporter Human Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells Using AAVS1 Safe Harbor Transcription Activator-Like Effector Nuclease. *Curr Protoc Stem Cell Biol*. 2014;29:5a.7.1-18. doi: 10.1002/9780470151808.sc05a07s29.
24. Yang L, Guell M, Byrne S, Yang JL, De Los Angeles A, Mali P, et al. Optimization of scarless human stem cell genome editing. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2013;41(19):9049-61. doi: 10.1093/nar/gkt555.
25. Andrews PW, Gokhale PJ. A short history of pluripotent stem cells markers. *Stem cell reports*. 2024;19(1):1-10. doi: 10.1016/j.stemcr.2023.11.012.
26. Paquet D, Kwart D, Chen A, Sproul A, Jacob S, Teo S, et al. Efficient introduction of specific homozygous and heterozygous mutations using CRISPR/Cas9. *Nature*. 2016;533(7601):125-9. doi: 10.1038/nature17664.
27. Richardson CD, Ray GJ, DeWitt MA, Curie GL, Corn JE. Enhancing homology-directed genome editing by catalytically active and inactive CRISPR-Cas9 using asymmetric donor DNA. *Nat Biotechnol*. 2016;34(3):339-44. doi: 10.1038/nbt.3481.
28. Brinkman EK, Chen T, de Haas M, Holland HA, Akhtar W, van Steensel B. Kinetics and Fidelity of the Repair of Cas9-Induced Double-Strand DNA Breaks. *Molecular cell*. 2018;70(5):801-13.e6. doi: 10.1016/j.molcel.2018.04.016.
29. Asmamaw Mengstie M, Teshome Azezew M, Asmamaw Dejenie T, Teshome AA, Tadele Admasu F, Behaile Teklemariam A, et al. Recent Advancements in Reducing the Off-Target Effect of CRISPR-Cas9 Genome Editing. *Biologics*. 2024;18:21-8. doi: 10.2147/btt.S429411.
30. Zhang XH, Tee LY, Wang XG, Huang QS, Yang SH. Off-target Effects in CRISPR/Cas9-mediated Genome Engineering. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids*. 2015;4(11):e264. doi: 10.1038/mtna.2015.37.
31. Guo C, Ma X, Gao F, Guo Y. Off-target effects in CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing. *Front Bioeng Biotechnol*. 2023;11:1143157. doi: 10.3389/fbioe.2023.1143157.
32. Nollet F, van Hengel J, Berx G, Molemans F, van Roy F. Isolation and characterization of a human pseudogene (CTNNAP1) for alpha E-catenin (CTNNA1): assignment of the pseudogene to 5q22 and the alpha E-catenin gene to 5q31. *Genomics*. 1995;26(2):410-3. doi: 10.1016/0888-7543(95)80231-a.

33. Karam R, Carvalho J, Bruno I, Graziadio C, Senz J, Huntsman D, et al. The NMD mRNA surveillance pathway downregulates aberrant E-cadherin transcripts in gastric cancer cells and in CDH1 mutation carriers. *Oncogene*. 2008;27(30):4255-60. doi: 10.1038/onc.2008.62.
34. Lykke-Andersen S, Jensen TH. Nonsense-mediated mRNA decay: an intricate machinery that shapes transcriptomes. *Nature reviews Molecular cell biology*. 2015;16(11):665-77. doi: 10.1038/nrm4063.
35. Denes CE, Cole AJ, Aksoy YA, Li G, Neely GG, Hesselson D. Approaches to Enhance Precise CRISPR/Cas9-Mediated Genome Editing. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2021;22(16). doi: 10.3390/ijms22168571.
36. Kim HS, Kweon J, Kim Y. Recent advances in CRISPR-based functional genomics for the study of disease-associated genetic variants. *Experimental & Molecular Medicine*. 2024;56(4):861-9. doi: 10.1038/s12276-024-01212-3.
37. Zhang JP, Li XL, Li GH, Chen W, Arakaki C, Botimer GD, et al. Efficient precise knockin with a double cut HDR donor after CRISPR/Cas9-mediated double-stranded DNA cleavage. *Genome biology*. 2017;18(1):35. doi: 10.1186/s13059-017-1164-8.
38. Xu H, Kita Y, Bang U, Gee P, Hotta A. Optimized electroporation of CRISPR-Cas9/gRNA ribonucleoprotein complex for selection-free homologous recombination in human pluripotent stem cells. *STAR Protoc*. 2021;2(4):100965. doi: 10.1016/j.xpro.2021.100965.
39. Leal AF, Herreno-Pachón AM, Benincore-Flórez E, Karunathilaka A, Tomatsu S. Current Strategies for Increasing Knock-In Efficiency in CRISPR/Cas9-Based Approaches. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2024;25(5). doi: 10.3390/ijms25052456.
40. Goullée H, Taylor RL, Forrest ARR, Laing NG, Ravenscroft G, Clayton JS. Improved CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing in primary human myoblasts using low confluency cultures on Matrigel. *Skeletal muscle*. 2021;11(1):23. doi: 10.1186/s13395-021-00278-1.
41. Lobo S, Dias A, Ferreira M, Herrera-Mullar J, Svrcek M, Hueneburg R, et al. 18P The role of CTNNA1 truncating variants in hereditary diffuse gastric cancer (HDGC). *Annals of Oncology*. 2024;35:S220. doi: 10.1016/j.annonc.2024.08.027.
42. Sarpal R, Pellikka M, Patel RR, Hui FY, Godt D, Tepass U. Mutational analysis supports a core role for *Drosophila* α -catenin in adherens junction function. *Journal of cell science*. 2012;125(Pt 1):233-45. doi: 10.1242/jcs.096644.

A

Clone: 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 10 11 12 13 16 17 18 20 23 24 CTR-

B

Clone no.*	Sequences found (N)	Sequence 1	Sequence 2
1	2	WT	Small indel
2	2	WT	Small indel
3	1	WT	-
4	1	WT	-
5	1	150bp deletion	-
6	1	150bp deletion	-
8	1	WT	Small indel
10	1	WT	-
11	1	WT	-
12	2	WT	Small indel
16	1	WT	Small indel
17	1	WT	-
18	2	WT	Small indel
20	1	WT	Small indel
23	1	WT	Small indel
24	2	WT	-

Supplementary Figure 1. Genotype analysis of CTNNA1P1 off-target site in edited clones. (A) Electrophoresis displaying the genotyping of the CTNNA1P1 sequence in the vicinity of the sgRNA off-target site. (B) Summary table of the CTNNA1P1 genetic sequences found in the edited clones by Sanger sequence.

Supplementary Table 1. List of recognized off-target sites for the sgRNA used in this study by the WTSI Genome Editing (WGE) software.

WGE ID	Location	Sequence	Mismatches	Strand	Type
998037642	Original CRISPR target (CTNNA1)	GATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	NA	+	Exonic
995744566	5:115390356-115390378	GATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	1	-	Intergenic
1130577250	15:85103670-85103692	GACAATTGCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	3	-	Intronic
1122735004	14:103833532-103833554	TCTCATGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	3	-	Intronic
1145062861	17:19743603-19743625	AATCTGGCTCTGCTTCCCC TGG	3	-	Intronic
1076840836	10:133044466-133044488	GACGATGGCTCAGCTTCCCC CGG	3	-	Intergenic
925845879	2:8032600-8032622	TATCATGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	3	-	Intergenic
1103457723	12:121079728-121079750	GATCATGGAGCAGCTTCCCC AGG	3	+	Intergenic
943668979	2:190640538-190640560	CATCATGACTCAGCTTACCC AGG	3	-	Intergenic
967694747	3:192516840-192516862	GACCATGGCTCAGGTTGCC TGG	3	-	Intronic
1052245473	9:26329140-26329162	AATCTGGCTCAGCTTACC TGG	3	+	Intergenic
1173352912	20:42261485-42261507	GGTCATGACTCAGCTTACC TGG	3	-	Intronic
943118812	2:183709186-183709208	GATCATGTCTCTGCTTCCC AGG	3	+	Intergenic
1048298752	8:133236004-133236026	CATCATGTCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	-	Intergenic
900035121	1:401426-401448	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	-	Intergenic
900056741	1:637179-637201	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	-	Intergenic
922257653	1:223906982-223907004	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	-	Intergenic
924338847	1:243009761-243009783	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	-	Intergenic
979238273	4:118425477-118425499	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	+	Intergenic
1002738698	5:181417445-181417467	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	+	Intergenic
1019243802	6:170692997-170693019	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	+	Intergenic
1035504321	8:115163-115185	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	-	Intergenic
1203603991	Un_K1270748v1:42220-42242	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	+	Intergenic
1202386048	Y:24327269-24327291	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	+	Intergenic
1202484738	Y:25342859-25342881	TATCATGGCTCAGCTTCCC TGG	3	-	Intergenic
991469860	5:66956410-66956432	GATCATGGCTTAGATTCCC GGG	3	+	Intronic
1181156644	22:20926380-20926402	GATCTGGCTCAGCTTCTCA GGG	3	-	Intronic
1168797324	20:620319-620341	CCCAGGGCTCAGCTTCCCC CGG	4	-	Intergenic
1152303328	17:79507852-79507874	CAGGAAGCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intronic
1185589020	X:1261570-1261592	GAGGGGGCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intergenic
1022247781	7:28577136-28577158	GCTAAGGCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1026674413	7:72417019-72417041	GATGGAAGCTCAGCTTCCCC GGG	4	+	Intronic
980095896	4:128490283-128490305	CACAATGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intergenic
1063877676	10:10497074-10497096	TCTCTGCCTCAGCTTCCCC TGG	4	-	Intergenic
1098247509	12:68535726-68535748	TCTCTGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intergenic
1148034978	17:44653394-44653416	TCTCTGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intergenic
927782362	2:2594997-25950019	TCTCTGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1174648813	20:52106987-52107009	TCTCTGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intronic
989445641	5:41525392-41525414	TCTCTGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intergenic
1052491851	9:29179511-29179533	TCTCTGCCTCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intergenic
1070819461	10:79346569-79346591	GTCCAGGCCTCAGCTTCCCC TGG	4	+	Intergenic
919894555	1:202001257-202001279	GATCAGAATCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intronic
1048213251	8:132474815-132474837	CACCTTGGCCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intronic
1138431513	16:56972104-56972126	GGGAGGGCCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1144842684	17:18197883-18197905	GAGGATGTCCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1107737255	13:43412869-43412891	GAACATCACCCAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Exonic
1053516671	9:38736162-38736184	TTTCATGGAACAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intergenic
1081460911	11:43272293-43272315	GATGAAGGACAGCTTCCCC TGG	4	+	Intergenic
1133248761	16:4466384-4466406	GATCAGCAGCAGCTTCCCC TGG	4	+	Exonic
1142212140	16:88813316-88813338	GCTCATGTGGCAGCTTCCCC GGG	4	-	Intergenic
1183357770	22:37368711-37368733	CCTCAGGGTGAAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Exonic
1018049597	6:159997360-159997382	CATCAGTGTGAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1118329755	14:64806077-64806099	CATCTGTCTGAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intronic
911253252	1:95604433-95604455	GATGAAGCCTGAGCTTCCCC GGG	4	+	Intergenic

963696729	3:148573102-148573124	GATCATCTGTAAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intergenic
1049029315	8:140022704-140022726	CATCCTGGCCAAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
955719317	3:61864897-61864919	TATCATGACAGAGCTTCCCC TGG	4	-	Intronic
1001696797	5:173676206-173676228	GGTCATGGTGGAGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intergenic
1003062500	6:2874617-2874639	GCTGAGGGCTCCGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intergenic
1113041443	13:106107535-106107557	GATTGTGATCGGCTTCCCC TGG	4	-	Intergenic
1169466557	20:5846255-5846277	GATCAGGTTTCTGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1197728863	X:129793931-129793953	GAGCCTGGCCCTGCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Exonic
1013431094	6:110055342-110055364	GACCTTTGCTCATCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intergenic
1118387554	14:65268930-65268952	GATCACAGCGCATCTTCCCC TGG	4	-	Intergenic
1157199460	18:45646723-45646745	GATCTTGCCACCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1044588052	8:93886204-93886226	GGTCATGGGGCACCTTCCCC TGG	4	-	Intronic
1166328130	19:42063557-42063579	GACCATGGAGCACCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
926146792	2:10401213-10401235	GATCTTTGCTCCCTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1176076118	20:63248964-63248986	GATCATGGGACCCTTCCCC CGG	4	-	Intronic
1184383987	22:44163936-44163958	GCCCCGGCTCAGGTTCCCC CGG	4	+	Intronic
1013211619	6:107992015-107992037	TGTCATAGCTCAGGTTCCCC GGG	4	+	Intergenic
920500648	1:206482971-206482993	TATCCTGCCTCAGGTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
1158609709	18:58928126-58928148	GAGCCTGTCTCAGTTTCCCC AGG	4	+	Intronic
999238159	5:150112446-150112468	CATCAGGCCTCAGTTTCCCC AGG	4	-	Intronic
929552697	2:42904528-42904550	GTTCAGGTCTCAGGTTCCCC GGG	4	+	Intergenic
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934742819	2:96738137-96738159	GATGATGGCTCAGCTTTCAG AGG	4	-	Intronic
942055138	2:172175004-172175026	GATCATGGCTCAGCTACATG AGG	4	+	Intergenic

Supplementary material

Protocol for preparing iPSCs for karyotype analysis

This protocol is for preparing cell cultures for karyotype analysis.

Multiple samples can be prepared in parallel using this protocol, reagent volumes should be adjusted according to the cell growth surface used.

A. List of reagents:

- Colcemid (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat 15210040); warm to 37°C prior to use
- TrypLE™ Express Enzyme (1X), no phenol red (e.g. Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat 12604013); warm to 37°C prior to use
- Pre-made 0.075 M KCl solution (e.g. Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat 10575090). Potassium Chloride Solution is formulated as 5.592 g potassium chloride per liter distilled water, filtrated with a 0,2 um filter; warm to 37°C prior to use
- Freshly prepared 3:1 Fixative (add 3 volumes of methanol to 1 volume acetic acid). Methanol (e.g. VWR, Cat 20847.307); Acetic Acid (e.g. VWR, cat 20103.330); chilled at -20°C, prior to use.
- Freshly prepared Peridrol Solution (300ml): 75ml of 35% hydrogen peroxide, 130 vol + 225ml of distilled water. Prepare daily and use at room temperature.
- Sorensen's Buffer: 9.47g sodium hydrogen phosphate dihydrate + 9.073g potassium dihydrogen phosphate + 1L distilled water. This buffer should be stored in the refrigerator at 4°C. Use at room temperature.
- Gurr's Buffer: 1 Gurr's Buffer tablet + 1L distilled water. This buffer should be stored in the refrigerator at 4°C. Use at room temperature.
- Freshly prepared Trypsin Solution for Leishman Staining: 360mg trypsin + 300ml Sorensen's buffer in a 250ml flask with a magnetic stir bar (10 minutes stirring). Prepare daily.
- Leishman Stain (Stock Solution): 0.75g Leishman stain + 100ml pure methanol. Stir this solution for 10 minutes. Add 400ml methanol (final volume = 500ml) and continue stirring for 24 hours. Let stand for 2 days. Leishman stain should be prepared in a 1000ml glass flask with a magnetic stir bar. All procedures involving preparation and use of the stain must be performed protected from light: weigh in darkness and wrap the glass flask in aluminum foil.
- Leishman Stain (Working Solution): Filter 75ml of Leishman stain (stock solution) through two filter papers into a 100ml graduated cylinder. Rinse the cylinder with 225ml Gurr's buffer and add to the stain (final volume = 300ml). Homogenize with a Pasteur pipette and allow a film to form on the surface of the stain (prepare daily).
- Fetal Bovine Serum – FBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat A5256801).

B. Cell requirements:

- For each sample, one well of a 6-well plate is required.
- For colony culture, colonies should be large enough to be visible by eye
- Culture should be in log phase, undergoing active cell division. Media should be changed 16 – 24 hours prior to harvesting to stimulate cell division.

C. Protocol:

1. Add pre-warmed 1980 of fresh media + 20 μ l colcemid per 6-well (10 μ g/ml).
2. Incubate at 37°C for 60 minutes.
3. Transfer 167 μ l of filtered FBS to a 15 ml centrifuge tube.
4. Add 667 μ l of pre-warmed TrypLE™ to the well. Rock gently for 5 – 10 seconds. Then transfer the cell suspension to the FBS containing centrifuge tube.
5. Add a further 667 μ l of pre-warmed TrypLE™ to the well and incubate for 8 – 10 minutes at 37°C. Monitor cell detachment. Try to produce a single cell suspension. If clusters do not break down to single cells, add an additional 333 μ l of pre-warmed TrypLE™ and incubate for an additional 2 – 3 minutes.
6. Transfer cell suspension to the centrifuge tube (containing FBS plus Trypsin-EDTA) prepared in steps 4 and 5 above.
7. Centrifuge the tube at 800 – 1000 rpm (approx. 150 x g) for 8 minutes.
8. Discard the supernatant and flick the tube 20 times to dislodge the cell pellet.
9. Using a 1 ml pipette add ~ 666 μ l ml pre-warmed 0.075 M KCl drop by-drop (1 drop/second), gently mix. Adjust total volume to ~1.3-1.5 ml with 0.075 M KCl in the same manner as before and gently mix again.
10. Incubate at 37°C for 25 minutes.

Note: After hypotonic treatment, cells are more fragile. Handle carefully.

11. Using a dropper, very slowly (1 drop/second), add 8 drops of cold fixative (3:1 methanol/acetic acid). Tilt the centrifuge tube and make sure the drops of fixative slide down the side of the tube into the mixture. Mix by gently inverting once or twice.
12. Incubate at room temperature for 10 minutes.
13. Centrifuge the tube at 800 – 1000 rpm (approx. 150 x g) for 8 minutes.
14. Discard the supernatant and flick tube 20 times to dislodge the cell pellet.
15. Very slowly (1 drop/second) with gentle mixing between each 3 drops, add 1 ml of cold fixative. Invert to mix. Adjust the volume of fixative drop by drop (1 drop/second) gentle mixing to 2 ml. Again, invert to mix.
16. Incubate sample at room temperature for 30 minutes.
17. Centrifuge the tube at 800 – 1000 rpm (approx. 150 x g) for 8 minutes.
18. Discard the supernatant and flick tube 20 times to dislodge the cell pellet.
19. Add 1.5 ml fixative. Swirl to mix.

20. Transfer the cell suspension to a 15 ml tube. If needed, at this point, fixed cells can be stored at 4°C.
21. For slide spreading use a Spreading Chamber (THERMOTRON) with temperature at 23°C and humidity at 42%. Take a small quantity of cell suspension (~20 ul) in a 20 ul pipette.
22. Release 1-3 drops in a row onto an alcohol cleaned slide, a single drop at a time.
23. Then, hold the slide vertically to allow excess fixative to drain off, placing the edge of the slide against filter paper.
24. Allow the slide to dry in an inclined position within the spreading chamber. Prepare at least 2 slides for each cell line cell line.
25. Place slides to age in a Chamber at 90°C for 1 hour.
26. GTL banding is performed on a Mirastainer Device (automatic method for staining). Place the Slides on the device arm (with the identification facing upwards).
27. Add the Solutions to their respective containers and set Program 5 (Tank 1: Peridrol – 3 min; Tank2: Methanol – 10 sec with agitation).
28. Then, remove slides from the arm and place them horizontally on the bench and allow to dry.
29. Next, return the slides to the arm and add the solutions to the respective containers and set Program 3 (Tank1: Trypsin – 4 sec; Tank 2: Sorensen – 12 sec; Tank 3: Leishman Stain – 10 min; Tank 4 – Gurr; Tank 5: running water – 3 sec; Tank 6: drying – 45°C, 2min).
30. Remove the slides from the arm and place them in a box. Wait for the slides to dry.
31. For cytogenetic analysis at least 20 metaphases are analysed, counting and analyzing the structure of all chromosomes by an experienced cytogeneticist in a Nikon Eclipse E400 microscope with CCD camera. At least 5 metaphases of which are captured and organized into a karyotype using the CytoVision software from Applied Imaging). The International System for Human Cytogenetic Nomenclature (ISCN, 2020) is followed for defining the chromosomal nomenclature.